

Masculinity and Heroism in Soyinka's Reworking of Oral Epics

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Abstract

This paper examines Wole Soyinka's depiction of masculinity and heroism through Yoruba oral epics, focusing on *A Dance of the Forests*, *Death and the King's Horseman*, and *The Man Died: Prison Notes*. Reworking traditional notions of male identity, Soyinka critiques indigenous and colonial constructions of masculinity, offering a sophisticated understanding of heroism. Using a feminist framework integrating masculinity studies and postcolonial theory, the study employs close reading and comparative analysis to examine themes of moral conflict, communal responsibility, and the interplay between myth and reality. Key findings reveal Soyinka's deconstruction of physical strength as the primary marker of heroism, replacing it with psychological depth, wisdom, and responsibility. His critique highlights the limitations of patriarchal and colonial ideologies, advocating a model of masculinity grounded in ethical leadership and reform. The paper recommends incorporating Soyinka's perspectives into gender and cultural studies, emphasizing their relevance to contemporary discussions on identity and power.

Keywords: Masculinity, Yoruba Oral Epics, Postcolonial Theory, Heroism and Moral Conflict